

THE IMPORTANCE OF DISCIPLINE IN THE EDUCATION OF SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Annotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada maktab o'quvchilari tartib-intizomining maktab va jamiyat hayotidagi ahamiyati va ta'lim olish jarayonidagi o'rni, intizomsizlikning jamiyat hayotiga va yurt kelajagiga salbiy ta'siri, tartib-intizomni va o'quv jarayonini yaxshilash uchun strategiyalar haqida fikr-mulohaza yuritiladi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** intizom, obro', motivatsiya, rol-model, birgalikdagi javobgarlik.*

***Аннотация:** В этой статье обсуждаются важность дисциплины школьников в жизни школы и общества и ее роль в процессе обучения, негативное влияние недисциплинированности на жизнь общества и будущее страны, а также стратегии улучшения дисциплины и учебного процесса.*

***Ключевые слова:** дисциплина, авторитет, мотивация, ролевая модель, совместная ответственность.*

***Annotation:** This article discusses the importance of school discipline at school and social life and its role in the educational process, the negative impacts of indiscipline on community and the future of the country, and strategies for improving discipline and educational process.*

***Key words:** Discipline, authority, motivation, role-model, joint-responsibility.*

Discipline is crucial in school environment for the learning process to take effect smoothly. Discipline in school system helps to produce well behaved male and female students who do not only respect themselves but also the school authorities and regulations of the school. Discipline is very essential for creating a positive school climate, learning process, academic performance and achievement. For the performance of students to be standard, they need to conform to the rules or conditions that are conducive to learning. For the on-going needs of qualified teachers and efficient trained good student to be achieved, specific orders and discipline should be maintained and followed for the production of standard teachers and learners. Standard

education is the only remedy to ignorance. And this can be achieved through effective discipline of teachers, learners in the learning environment.

The concept of discipline can be viewed from several points of view. Each person perceives discipline otherwise- simply as obedience, or as a set of rules of behavior, or as a set of habits acquired through education for example. These views are – to a greater – but also lesser extent, close to the truth.(Makarenko, Anton Semenovich. *O vychove deti v rodine*. Praha: SPN, 1957).

One of the important aspects is Pedagogical Discipline, which is closely, associated with education. Pedagogical discipline is especially aimed at children; and thereby, the given nature to submit to authority. When talking about disciplinary goals, it is thus, understood that discipline should create a useful member of the state from a pupil, and create a well-structured life of a student, and has to teach them what the state wants from them as citizens, i.e. obedience to the laws.(Uher, Jan. *Problem kazne*. V Praze: Dedictvi Komenskeho, 1924.218 s.). Managing pupils' discipline has been a big challenge and concern to many parents, teachers and the whole society. Indiscipline of learners disrupts also well-mannered pupils and causes them to get spoiled. As time goes on, these pupils become adults and the future of the state will be connected to them. So, the government must regulate such kind of acts or misbehaviors with laws strictly.

One of the important features in creating a positive climate in the classroom, which acts on pupils' discipline, is motivation. Just as the teacher's authority is important, so too is it also important to motivate students to not even think about improper conduct. In the course of the motivation process, it is important that students be motivated from several sides. This has to do with internal motivation, external motivation and the expected success of the pupil.(KYRIACOU, Chris. *Klichove dovednosti uchitele: cesty k lepsimu vyuchovani*. Praha, 1996.153 s.) No doubt that the pupils should be inspired. However, to give motivation to the youth, the teachers are expected to be motivated, well-behaved, qualified and they must be paid enough salary for their work.

Schools face a number of challenges related to disruptive and antisocial pupils. The behavior of these pupils interferes with learning, diverts administrative time, and contributes to teacher burnout (Byrne, 1999; Kendziora & Osher, 2009).In order to cope with such kind of problems, the government, the school and the parents should work together. There must be respect among teachers and parents. There are very serious problems related to indiscipline in the educational system of Uzbekistan. The cause is that the environment of some families are not satisfying, the children's

behaviors are irritating. The parents even do not respect teachers. The teachers' authority must be increased in that case.

School discipline entails more than punishment. It is complex and includes developing student *self-discipline* (Bear, 2005). It is known that corporal punishment is banned at schools of our country. It is true that this is contrary to the democratic tendencies and human rights. On the one hand, the young learners are growing up independently and without fear. On the other hand, if teachers punish the ill-behaved pupils by just lowering the mark or rebuke them for their indiscipline, the parents are supporting their children and disrespect the teachers.

Strategies to promote good discipline and effective learning

There are many other strategies used and considered in promoting good discipline and effective learning. They are outlined as following:

1. Appropriate levels of Supervision— Supervision levels depend on the context, age of students and tasks:
 - a. Students are engaged with Classroom activities.
 - b. Strong positive support for learning and mutual respect among teachers and students .
 - c. The classroom is free of negative personal comment or put-downs.
 - d. Students demonstrate autonomy and initiative so that attention to the discipline and regulation of student behavior is required.
 - e. Pupils are taught what is expected and, agree to classroom values and rules.
2. Effective learning programs- Lessons are conducted in a stimulating learning climate based on the school syllabus designed to meet student needs.
3. Routines— these are expected procedures which help to make school activities efficient and orderly thereby protecting the rights of students and teachers.
4. Teachers as Positive Role Models— Teachers are expected to strive to be role models demonstrating responsible, caring and consistent behavior for students.
6. Parent Involvement Communication— parents have an important role to play in assisting with learning and promoting acceptable behavior in their children. Parents are expected to:
 - a. Accept joint responsibility, with the school, for the education of their Children.
 - b. Develop positive attitudes to school in their children.
 - c. Look after the physical, social and emotional needs of their children, So that they are ready and able to do their best at school.
 - d. Be a positive role model.

Summing up, teachers or school administrators and pupils are the major instruments to improve discipline in school environment. Therefore, school-community relationship is also important in building appropriate discipline. This is due to opportunity given to parent to resist school regularly. Mostly Parent-Teacher Association meetings can be of help to share idea of checking indiscipline in the schools. Teachers need to upgrade themselves in their teaching methodologies and serve as role model in the area of dressing, immoral relationship with the students. To have great turn around in pupils' learning process and improvement on standard education, the Government should adopt a decree that prohibits and punishes the parents who disrespect teachers!

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